

ASPECTS OF DOCUMENTATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL ITEMS IN THE STATE ART MUSEUM OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731351>

Abstract. *This article examines the current problems of documenting archaeological items in the State Museum of Arts of Uzbekistan. This topic has not been sufficiently studied in domestic museology, which determines its relevance. Nevertheless, there is a fairly broad scientific base, consisting mainly of foreign studies on this issue. In this regard, a comparison is made with the experience of foreign countries.*

Keywords: *museum, collection, archaeological items, Accession Book, keeper, act, inventory book, code.*

Introduction. Museum collections represent a complex system that includes items stored in museum funds and those displayed in exhibitions. The total number of archaeological monuments that fall into the fund of the State Museum of Arts of Uzbekistan is more than 100 thousand, of which more than 20 thousand archeological fund materials are stored. In addition, it comprises items temporarily loaned for exhibitions, as well as objects sent for examination or restoration. Each of these groups has varying social significance and plays a different role in the activities of the museum.

The process of accepting archaeological finds into museum collections and their subsequent storage remains a vital issue. To regulate this process, several legal and sub-legal documents have been adopted by the government. The archaeological items are submitted to the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan according to these documents, their acceptance is based on a series of regulations, including the Decree No. PD-1913 of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from January 12, 1998, titled "About the Fundamental Improvement and Development of Museum Activities", the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About Museums" (2008), and the Cabinet of Ministers' resolutions No. 237 from October 31, 2010, and No. 68 from April 14, 2010, as well as the guidelines "About the Inventory, Storage, and Restoration of Museum Items and Collections". [1]

Data collected during the study of museum items are recorded in accounting documents such as the accession book, inventory book, acceptance records, card indexes, and catalogs. [2, 6] The process of documenting items is uniformly carried out across all museums in Uzbekistan. Following the conclusion of the Museum fund management and Acquisition commission, a decision is made as to which fund the item is to be accepted into. If necessary, the item is restored and then placed in the exhibition hall.

Upon examining international experience in the documentation of museum objects, particularly in countries such as the UK [3], Russia [4], Belarus [5], and Kazakhstan [6], it is evident that the process of object acceptance is largely similar to the system practiced in Uzbekistan.

Andrew Roberts, who headed the Information Resources Department at a London museum and was an active member of the International Committee for Documentation (ICOM-CIDOC),

spent over thirty years working in museum documentation. His standards and systems are widely applied in museum operations. In his article *"Accounting and Documentation"*, Roberts outlined practical guidance for museum recordkeeping. He emphasized the need for continued documentation throughout an object's life, including research and usage.

A standard classification table based on set guidelines allows for effective tracking of an object's movement and preservation status. Taking into account local specificities of Uzbekistan's museums, Roberts' classification and documentation models—especially for art objects—can be adapted and used widely. The table, which contains seven sections, can serve as a standardized documentation system for all museums housing artistic artifacts. According to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, museum objects and collections that are part of the main fund are considered inalienable elements of the cultural heritage of the people. They cannot be lost, exchanged, or damaged, except in cases where items were mistakenly included in the main fund based on inaccurate expert conclusions or in accordance with court decisions [7, 36].

According to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, museum items and museum collections included in the main fund are an integral part of the cultural heritage of the people of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and their spontaneous disappearance is not permitted. Museum items and museum collections included in the main fund belong to the state part of the Museum Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Items in the archaeological fund include objects made from stone, ceramics, metal, bone, glass, and wood that help uncover historical insights. These are listed in the museum's accession book based on information from field documentation and acceptance records. Before filling in the accession book, it is formally prepared: pages are numbered, bound with a thick thread, sealed with wax or covered with paper, and stamped with the museum seal. All entries must be written clearly, and corrections are not allowed unless they are clearly marked and justified. Minor corrections must be explained in the remarks section and signed by the museum director, head custodian, accounting head, and item custodian.

After registration, the objects are handed over to fund custodians under material responsibility and further subjected to inventory—the second stage of documentation [9, 7-8]. This step, involving the scientific inventory book, is crucial for the classification, description, and identification of items.

During the study of archaeological items, their distinguishing features, location of discovery, environmental context, cultural attribution, period, ornamentation, and symbolic content are taken into account.

The main documents for inventory include:

- Accession Book (AB),
- Inventory Book (INB),
- Special Inventory Book for objects made of precious metals and stones (SIB),
- Fund List,
- Archival Lists (similar to inventory books),
- Acceptance and Transfer Acts (for temporary or permanent use).

Changes made to the procedure for recording archaeological monuments in the state museum of arts of Uzbekistan are recorded in the Memorandum "On making changes to accounting documents". Storage or use of undocumented museum objects is strictly prohibited. Any amendments made to inventory documents are recorded in a specific statement and reviewed

by the Fund Management and Acquisition Commission. Changes are authorized and signed by the head custodian and sealed by the museum.

Archaeological items accepted into the museum are assigned unique accession numbers, which are considered their official registration codes. Short technical descriptions, including distinctive characteristics, material, technique, size, and preservation condition, are entered into the accession book. In cases of theft or loss, these records aid in identification and recovery.

For large sets of similar items, a general entry may be made in the accession book, with individual numbers noted fractionally (e.g., 1/1, 1/2, etc.). These items are also listed individually in a separate catalog stored in bound volumes in the accounting department. After inventory registration, responsible custodians label each item with its assigned inventory code using data from the accession and inventory books. For example, an item may be marked as 111/5555 in the collection register and A1-3333 in the inventory book.

Items received for temporary storage—such as for exhibition or restoration—are assigned temporary codes written in pencil or attached with tags. Older codes are retained for reference but are crossed out using colored ink or pencil to ensure readability. In case of theft or loss of archaeological items, the museum must inform the Cultural Heritage Agency of Uzbekistan within three days. The agency reserves the right to verify submitted documentation and may conduct spot-checks of items or collections. Each item brought to the museum must first be documented and then transferred to the appropriate fund department. It is also necessary to review the deadlines for entering accepted items into the inventory book.

Conclusion. The study of the problems of documenting archaeological items in the State Museum of Arts of Uzbekistan allowed us to draw the following conclusions. This topic has not been sufficiently studied in domestic museology, which determines its relevance. The research results presented by the author may be useful for a more in-depth study of the topic.

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